

The Dual Role of Vitamin C Against Pseudomonas aeruginosa: A Systematic Review of Mechanisms and Antibiotic Interactions

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ABSTRACT

Pseudomonas aeruginosa (*P. aeruginosa*) is characterized by high pathogenicity and its efficient development of antibiotic resistance complicates control of this pathogen. For decades, vitamins have been explored as potential antibacterial agents.

This review, the first systematic analysis of literature published since 2000, reveals the therapeutic potential of Vitamin C against *P. aeruginosa*. Analysis of 26 studies highlights its diverse, dose- and strain-dependent interactions with antibiotics and identifies significant methodological limitations in the existing literature. The current data from *in vitro* and *in vivo* models are promising, which is why we encourage continued research on the use of vitamins in combating bacterial infections.

Keywords: *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, antibiotics, vitamin c, antibiotic resistance, altmed

INTRODUCTION

The problem of antimicrobial resistance is a topic that the scientific community has been grappling with for many decades. The adaptive capabilities of bacteria were highlighted as early as 1945 by Fleming himself [1]. One of the species with a notable ability to develop resistance is *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (*P. aeruginosa*).

In 1913, the Polish biochemist Kazimierz Funk formulated the concept of a vitamin. About two decades later, interest in vitamins grew to the level of seeking their therapeutic potential. Influential figures from various scientific fields, though their views remain criticized to this day, saw significant therapeutic potential in them; these include, among others, Pauling [2], Hoffer [3], Cathcart [4] and Klenner [5,6].

Today, the movement promoting megadoses of vitamins still operates in many developed countries, often propelled by authors of popular alternative medicine publications. A case in point is Jerzy Zięba, an author whose works have gained significant popularity in Poland and are available internationally. Such claims, however, typically lack the support of rigorous clinical studies. Clinical practice (EBM), however, does not completely reject the concept of using vitamins in therapy but maintains the position that they can only be an adjunctive element.

One of the most popular vitamins, which was considered, among other things, as a therapeutic for cancer, is vitamin C. Interest in vitamins, including therapies using vitamin C, increased during the COVID-19 pandemic [see supplementary materials]. It was then that the alternative medicine community proposed treating not only viral infections with it but also bacterial infections, including those caused by *P. aeruginosa*.

Vitamin C is not only supplemented today as ascorbic acid but also in the form of its salts or nanoemulsions (e.g., liposomal vitamin C). Humans do not have the ability for endogenous vitamin synthesis due to a mutation in the *GULO* gene [7]. For this reason, supplementation is necessary and usually takes the form of food additives. Oral supplementation has two main limitations – variable bioavailability [8] and low achievable plasma concentrations [9]. The issue of bioavailability is still a subject of research, and a promising solution seems to be nanotechnology and nanoemulsions. Administering vitamin C intravenously allows for much higher concentrations, usually in the range of 16-28 mM with doses of tens to 100g [9,10] – although the scientific community is not in agreement about the maximum plasma concentrations. The pharmacokinetics is a complex and interesting aspect, encompassing, among other things, the variability of the half-life ($T_{1/2}$) or the higher reabsorption of the vitamin in oncology patients [11,12].

P. aeruginosa originates from the genus *Pseudomonas* with broad industrial applications [13–15]. The physiology of the species is complex, but the most important aspects include the ability to develop resistance and to compete with other

species using components of the Quorum Sensing system, for which the compound 3-oxo-C12-HSL is an important mediator [16]. *P. aeruginosa* produces various pigments; one of the most important is pyocyanin, which is actively involved in biofilm formation and acting as a siderophore [17]. The work by Tenover et al. highlights the problem of this species, estimating that 30% of clinical isolates in the US are carbapenem-resistant [18]. In turn, carbapenem-resistant strains are often additionally resistant to β -lactamase inhibitors, fluoroquinolones, or aminoglycosides. In 2017, *P. aeruginosa* was designated by the WHO as a species of critical importance [19]. Due to WHO's methodology, after 7 years, it was moved to a lower position in the priority species ranking [20]. This internal WHO classification, however, does not change the fact that *P. aeruginosa* is a resistant opportunistic pathogen that attacks the skin, respiratory, circulatory, and nervous systems, easily leading to sepsis [21,22]. CLSI recommendations indicate basing therapy on β -lactams, aminoglycosides, fluoroquinolones, or tetracyclines.

A broader analysis of the social situation, the characteristics of the vitamin, or P. aeruginosa is available in the supplementary materials.

AIM OF THE REVIEW

Considering that improperly treated bacterial and viral infections pose a potential threat to human health and life, and the methods promoted in Zięba's materials are often not supported by relevant clinical studies, his materials were analyzed, and a thesis was selected for verification.

Jerzy Zięba, in the book "Ukryte Terapie. Czego ci lekarz nie powie cz. 2" (Hidden Therapies. What Your Doctor Won't Tell You Part 2), in the chapter "Mało znane mechanizmy działania witaminy C", claims that Vitamin C plays a significant role in treating infections caused by *P. aeruginosa*. He references the study "Rawal BD, Bactericidal action of ascorbic acid on *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*: alteration of cell surface as a possible mechanism. Chemotherapy. 1978; 24(3): 166-171." [23]. In the cited paper, Rawal asserted that ascorbate affects selected cell structures and elements through interaction with magnesium ions, leading to increased susceptibility to antibiotics and disruption of bacterial cell development.

Therefore, a review of current scientific literature was conducted to verify this claim and objectively consider the validity of using Vitamin C in treating bacterial infections caused by *P. aeruginosa*. Additionally, this work addresses a current problem in scientific literature: the lack of a comprehensive analysis of previously published experimental works on the aforementioned topic. In this study, we highlight previous findings from experimental models, identify errors in research methodologies with suggestions for their improvement, and determine the justification for further development of research directions concerning Vitamin C in antibiotic therapy.

METHODS

Based on Jerzy Zięba's books and statements found on social media, the claim referenced earlier in the text was derived. To verify this thesis, scientific literature was collected between November 2024 and May 2025 using Google Scholar, SCOPUS, and PubMed databases, as well as the Google search engine. Works were searched manually and via the Publish or Perish 8 software. The search targeted scientific papers containing the following keyword combinations:

1. "Vitamin C"
2. "ascorbate"
3. "ascorbic"
4. "pseudomonas aeruginosa"

The aforementioned databases were used due to their extensive collections and accessibility. Works were selected based on their title and meta description. The availability of the full text was the basis for a more detailed analysis, and only works written in English were analyzed. Filtering was applied only for the earliest publication date, which was set at 2000.

The analyzed literature included only experimental works focusing on the effect of Vitamin C on *P. aeruginosa* or the efficacy of antibiotics in combating it in *in vitro* or *in vivo* models. For this purpose, only works whose methodology allowed for assessing changes in bacterial behavior and antibiotic efficacy after adding Vitamin C to the environment were included. Both *in vitro* and *in vivo* models were accepted. Both peer-reviewed and non-peer-reviewed works were considered.

Due to the limited amount of available literature, the acceptance of studies was conducted with high tolerance regarding their methodology; any reservations are discussed in the Discussion chapter. Works that used models with a narrow range of tested substance concentrations, as well as those that included a wide spectrum of concentrations, were accepted. In cases where a work used an *in vivo* animal model, attention was paid to ensure the model included a control group not supplemented with Vitamin C; one exception to this rule was made due to the low number of such models.

The selection of works for analysis occurred in two stages:

1. Preliminary: The title had to indicate the use of Vitamin C in studies concerning *P. aeruginosa*. If the title indicated the use of antioxidant compounds, the meta description was also analyzed.
2. Final: Analysis of the abstract, methodology, and full text.

Studies were not excluded based on the journals in which they were published. Works published before 2000 were not considered.

Finally, using Publish or Perish, a register of 1048 publications was prepared, from which 144 were removed as they were duplicates from another database. Duplicate titles were detected and removed using Microsoft Excel's functions. The remaining 904 entries underwent preliminary analysis as described above. Due to title or meta description inconsistency with the subject of this work, or because the analysis included natural compounds like plant extracts, 883 works were excluded. Through manual searching, a total of 7 works were selected for detailed analysis, of which 2 were excluded due to suspected plagiarism.

Figure 5 – diagram based on PRISMA 2020 template.

Due to varying practices in reporting the quantity and concentrations of vitamins used, values were standardized to molar concentrations; these values were not converted for *in vivo* models. The above methodology naturally has certain limitations, which are discussed in the Discussion section.

RESULTS

We found and analyzed a total of 26 studies on the effects of Vitamin C on the physiology of *P. aeruginosa* and its antibiotic susceptibility. We excluded studies involving natural substances like honey or plant extracts due to their complex composition, which would make it impossible to determine which specific substance Vitamin C interacts with synergistically, antagonistically, or neutrally. A primary challenge in this collective analysis is the diversity of bacterial strains studied, leading to varied bacterial responses to chemical agents. The significant majority of analyzed studies indicate potential benefits of using Vitamin C as an adjunctive therapy to antibiotic treatment.

The collected literature utilized both ascorbic acid and sodium ascorbate. The final concentrations used in the studies ranged from 10-568 mM and 15.9-2020 mM, respectively. Due to the frequent lack of precise identification of isolates, it's impossible to provide an exact count of the strains or isolates used.

IN VITRO MODELS: COMBINATION OF VITAMIN C AND ANTIBIOTICS

The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values for both Vitamin C and antibiotics vary and depend on the specific *P. aeruginosa* strain/isolate used in the assays. For instance, Abdelraheem's study highlights the diverse susceptibility to Vitamin C among different *P. aeruginosa* strains [24].

Vitamin C can disrupt biofilm formation [24–32]. The primary mechanism behind this involves reducing the expression of genes crucial for biofilm development. However, Diaz De Rienzo suggests that Vitamin C's action might be limited to the initial stages of cell adhesion to a surface [30]. This effect has been observed when bacterial cultures were treated with Vitamin C alone, as well as when Vitamin C was combined with antibiotics. Additionally, data indicate that sodium ascorbate can reduce the level of 3-oxo-C12-HSL and downregulate the expression of QS-related genes [25].

Two of the *in vitro* investigations indicated an antagonistic effect between Vitamin C and antibiotics. A common element in these studies was the use of fluoroquinolone antibiotics, specifically Norfloxacin and Ciprofloxacin, which are structurally very similar. It was observed that combining these antibiotics with Vitamin C at a concentration of 10 mM reduced the zone of inhibition compared to trials where the antibiotic was used alone [33,34]. In contrast, a study using a combination of 1 mg/ml Ciprofloxacin and 20 mg/ml (i.e., 113.5 mM) ascorbic acid showed a synergistic effect [24]. Abbas's research, on the other hand, suggests that Vitamin C can have a neutral or synergistic impact on Ciprofloxacin, Cefoperazone, Tobramycin, Amikacin, and Imipenem, depending on the concentrations used and the isolate being tested [35]. However, Abbas's study itself raises several concerns, which are discussed in the discussion section.

Another fluoroquinolone antibiotic tested was Levofloxacin. One investigation, involving two *P. aeruginosa* strains obtained from patient catheters, demonstrated that combining $\frac{1}{4}$ MIC of Levofloxacin with 100 mg/ml of ascorbic acid (i.e., 568 mM) could achieve up to a 100% reduction in bacterial cell adhesion to catheter surfaces. Additionally, combining 2xMIC of Levofloxacin with 100 mg/ml of ascorbic acid allowed for up to a 98% reduction of mature biofilm. This particular research framework also indicates that susceptibility to both antibiotics and Vitamin C can vary depending on the *P. aeruginosa* strain [36].

Similar findings come from a very comparable experimental setup. Catheters were treated with either the antibiotic alone (Levofloxacin or Gentamicin), ascorbic acid alone, or in combinations. This reduced the bacterial count adhering to their surfaces. The combination of antibiotic and Vitamin C significantly enhanced this effect, achieving a reduction of >90% even at the lowest concentrations, specifically 20 mg/ml [37].

However, the behavior of Levofloxacin with Vitamin C, similar to other fluoroquinolone antibiotics, is not straightforward. Data exist indicating that in 4 out of 5 tested strains, the addition of 1 mg/ml of ascorbic acid to the sample increased the MIC value for Levofloxacin or Meropenem. This research suggests that Vitamin C may not influence antibiotic efficacy, and can even decrease it, with greater benefits stemming from the addition of N-acetylcysteine to the samples [38]. Chloramphenicol also exhibits varied behavior, showing synergism or antagonism with ascorbic acid depending on the specific strain used [39].

Tazobactam, Ceftazidime, and Piperacillin demonstrated synergism with ascorbic acid at a concentration of 20 mg/ml [24]. Synergism between 1 mg/ml (i.e., 5.68 mM) ascorbic acid and Kanamycin, Tetracycline, and Streptomycin was observed, though not across all tested strains. No benefit was found from combining Tobramycin and Ampicillin with 1 mg/ml Vitamin C, regardless of the strain used [39].

Concurrently, the authors of the cited studies emphasize that the occurrence of synergism or antagonism between Vitamin C and an antibiotic can be dependent on the specific bacterial strain studied [39] and that the number of strains examined was limited [34].

IN VITRO STUDIES: OTHER FINDINGS

Vitamin C, when used alone, can inhibit bacterial growth [29]. However, this study highlights the influence of physical and chemical factors, noting that an increase in temperature and pH can negatively affect the vitamin's efficacy. Solutions containing only Vitamin C can similarly impact even antibiotic-resistant strains [40].

Derivatives of ascorbic acid with greater stability also exist; one example is its ethyl derivative. However, these derivative compounds may possess different properties. The aforementioned ethyl derivative of ascorbic acid may only reduce bacterial titers starting from a concentration of 1.25 mg/ml (i.e., 6.12 mM), whereas ascorbic acid demonstrated this ability at concentrations as low as 0.3125 mg/ml (i.e., 1.774 mM) [41].

An experimental setup has also been published demonstrating that ascorbic acid solutions at concentrations ranging from 0.5-1% exhibit bactericidal activity against *P. aeruginosa*. Each tested concentration was capable of killing >93% of bacterial cells in liquid cultures after just 30 minutes, which was confirmed by plating on solid media [42]

Table 1 – simplified comparison of the results of combining Vitamin C and antibiotics

MAIN GROUP	SUBGROUP	NAME	RESULTS
β-lactams	Peniciline	Piperacillin	Synergism [24]
		Piperacillin/Tazobactam	Synergism [24]
		Ampicillin	Neutral [39]
	Cefalosporines	Ceftazidime	Synergism [24]
		Cefoperazone	Synergism [35]
	Carbapenemes	Imipenem	Synergism [35]
Meropenem		Neutral or antagonism [38]	
Aminoglycosides		Gentamicin	Synergism [37]
		Kanamycin	Synergism depends on isolate [39]
		Streptomycin	Synergism depends on isolate [39]
		Tobramycin	Neutral or antagonism [39]
		Amikacin	Synergism [35]
Fluoroquinolones		Ciprofloxacin	Synergism depends on the isolate and dose [24,34,35]
		Norfloxacin	Antagonism [33]
		Levofloxacin	Synergism depends on dose [36–38]
Tetracyclines		Tetracycline	Synergism depends on isolate [39]

Although furanone-30 is not currently used in clinical practice, it's worth noting that at concentrations not exceeding 100 μM and in combination with ascorbic acid (up to 70 mM), it can reduce pyocyanin activity, hemolysin activity, and the cell's ability to adhere or produce biofilm [28]. A separate experimental setup indicates that 10 mM ascorbic acid can also decrease pyomelanin production, and when combined with gallic acid, it additionally has the ability to reduce biofilm production. Significantly, gallic acid without Vitamin C can actually enhance pyomelanin production [43]. It is also possible

to reduce pyocyanin production by bacterial cells without using other compounds; one study points to a 38% reduction with the application of 150 µg/ml (0.852 mM) of Vitamin C in an unspecified form [44].

It's also possible to weaken the adhesion capabilities of bacterial cells to animal cells. This was demonstrated in an investigation examining the adhesion ability of bacterial isolates from urine to buccal epithelial cells. The results indicate that ascorbic acid at concentrations of 0.005 and 0.5 mg/ml (i.e., 0.0284 and 2.84 mM) can weaken the degree of adhesion. In the case of *P. aeruginosa*, bacterial proliferation in the presence of Vitamin C did not affect the outcome. However, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (*K. pneumoniae*) proliferation under these conditions resulted in enhanced adhesion to epithelial cells [45].

Vitamin C can also interact synergistically with inorganic compounds, such as ZnO. The combination of Vitamin C and zinc oxide was able to reduce the MIC for the vitamin by as much as 100-fold. Additionally, this combination prevented the negative impact of Vitamin C on the viability of HepG2 cells [29].

Another compound with bactericidal and bacteriostatic activities is nitric oxide. An analysis of urine samples enriched with 10 mM ascorbic acid showed increased production of this oxide, which prevented bacterial growth [46].

IN VIVO STUDIES

Among the analyzed research, some also examined the interaction of Vitamin C with antibiotics in *in vivo* models. The inclusion of Vitamin C in therapy demonstrated a positive effect in these animal studies.

One study that combined antibiotic therapy (Ceftazidime 20 mg/kg/day) with Vitamin C supplementation (ascorbic acid 200 mg/kg/day) proved that this combination most effectively combats inflammation and swelling in lung tissue, compared to groups treated with Vitamin C alone or antibiotic alone [24].

Another study was found where 500 mg of Vitamin C (the authors did not specify the form of the vitamin) was administered daily along with 20 mg of quercetin, without antibiotic therapy. This experiment showed an increase in rat survival from 0% to 70% and a reduction in bacterial titer in tissues by one order of magnitude [47].

The third *in vivo* investigation provides several significant insights. The main experimental group consisted of mice placed in hyperoxic conditions (>95% oxygen) for 24 hours, after which they began receiving sodium ascorbate intraperitoneally at 50 mg/kg/12h. After a total of 48 hours in hyperoxic conditions, the animals were infected intratracheally with the PAO1 strain and transferred to normal conditions (21% O₂). After another 18 hours, some of the animals were euthanized, and tissue samples were collected. Mice treated with Vitamin C exhibited lower bacterial titers in the lungs and respiratory tract; such a significant reduction in titer was not obtained in another experimental group where mice were treated with Vitamin C but were not exposed to hyperoxic conditions. Mice kept in hyperoxic conditions showed significantly reduced survival within 56 hours, regardless of receiving Vitamin C, compared to the control group (21% O₂). Additionally, this study analyzed the activity of RAW 264.7 macrophages in an *in vitro* system. It was noted that treating cells with high oxygen concentrations reduced phagocytosis intensity; however, this effect could be completely abrogated by exposing the cells to 1 mM ascorbic acid. Vitamin C also helped reduce levels of HMGB1 protein, which impacts the intensity of phagocytosis [48].

The last animal study analyzed used guinea pigs, which were kept on a diet with either adequate Vitamin C supplementation (i.e., 800 mg/kg body weight) or a reduced dose (i.e., 100 mg/kg body weight); the form of vitamin was not specified. There were 18 animals in each group. The animals were infected with strain 66999E, derived from a cystic fibrosis patient, in the form of alginate beads placed directly in the animals' lungs. It was observed that the group on the adequately supplemented Vitamin C diet showed higher survival rates, though there was no significant reduction in bacterial titer in the lungs. The authors also highlight a decreased level of Vitamin C in the lungs and plasma of the animals during infection. This drop may signal increased utilization of Vitamin C by granulocytes (PMN), which can use it to reduce hydrogen peroxide, thereby preventing excessive ROS production. Furthermore, a diet with higher Vitamin C content resulted in a better (i.e.,

lower) ratio of PMN to mononuclear leukocytes (MN), which — as the study authors indicate — may provide a basis for better prognosis [49].

The Mosallam et al. study, previously cited for its *in vitro* findings on Vitamin C's action, also included *in vivo* analysis. Mosallam demonstrated that implementing a sodium ascorbate nanoemulsion into the therapy of infected mice led to an increase in *P. aeruginosa* titer in the liver and kidneys, compared to the control. This effect was not observed in mice infected with *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*). As the researchers emphasize, further analyses are necessary to explain this result [27].

RAWAL'S CLAIM

There's a claim about Vitamin C's mechanism of action in enhancing antibiotic effectiveness that closely aligns with Rawal's assertion. The authors suggest that increased antibiotic efficacy might be due to Vitamin C's influence on: 1) protein synthesis within the cell wall components, and 2) hydrogen peroxide production resulting from ascorbate oxidation [24]. Given that hydrogen peroxide can decompose into hydroxyl radicals, the role of reactive oxygen species (ROS) in antibiotic therapy has been analyzed in the discussion.

Following a preliminary analysis of available, contemporary literature, we conclude that no existing studies confirm Rawal's thesis that Vitamin C's action involves interaction with magnesium ions. While data from his original study might suggest this, there's a lack of other experimental investigations verifying these reports.

Figure 6 – graphical representation of the effects of the implementation of Vitamin C

DISCUSSION

GENERAL CONCLUSIONS

The analyzed literature indicates that Vitamin C can serve as an element of antibiotic therapy and increase its effectiveness. However, more extensive *in vitro* and *in vivo* research is required to determine:

- Standardized MIC values for specific strains.
- Which antibiotics does Vitamin C exhibit synergistic action with, and which it acts antagonistically with, when combined.

- At what concentrations of Vitamin C and a given antibiotic the combination has a synergistic or antagonistic character in combating a particular strain.
- The safety profile of such therapy in animals and humans

MAIN PROBLEMS OF ANALYZED STUDIES AND METHODOLOGY

The low popularity of the discussed topic naturally leads to a limited amount of available scientific literature. For this reason, a certain tolerance regarding the methodology or origin of some of the discussed experimental studies was adopted. The most important reservations, along with exemplary studies to which they refer, include:

- Lack of information about the studied strain and/or lack of more precise differentiation of the tested isolates [24,38,39,47]
- Lack of information about the form of vitamin administered [29,44,47]
- Lack of MIC values for antibiotics or Vitamin C [35]
- Incompleteness of provided data, preventing independent analysis and calculations [31,35]
- Testing only one concentration or a narrow range of vitamin/antibiotic concentrations [33,34,43]
- Lack of data on Vitamin C concentrations in the animal's plasma [47]

In light of the above, it is suggested that the methodology of future studies in this field should include, among other things:

- Precise morphological, physiological, and genetic analysis of the studied strains.
- Specification of the form of vitamin and antibiotics used, along with information on the concentrations employed.
- Analysis of a wide range of concentrations for the vitamins and antibiotics under investigation, using small intervals.
- Regular monitoring of the Vitamin C concentration in the animal's plasma.

The analysis of currently available literature indicates the critical importance of precisely specifying the bacterial strain being studied. This stems from the fact that, as research shows, different isolates react differently to a given combination of vitamins and antibiotics. Furthermore, the analyzed studies indicate that certain doses may not negatively affect bacteria; instead, they might even induce, for example, biofilm formation, cell proliferation [41], or promote the creation of structures like capsular components [50].

Given the current state of data availability, an objective and reliable statistical analysis of the findings is not possible. The chosen methodology increases the risk of including data from improperly designed studies in the analysis.

We believe that reports published in less popular journals and raising certain concerns should be secondarily verified through independent experiments, and the obtained results subjected to meticulous peer review. This stems from the fact that during the literature collection, two Iranian papers were identified with justified suspicions of plagiarism of results [51,52].

ROLE OF REACTIVE OXYGEN SPECIES (ROS) IN ANTIBIOTIC THERAPY

Aerobic metabolism is continuously linked to the formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS). The most dangerous among these is the hydroxyl radical, which can arise from the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide. The role of ROS in combating bacteria is still under investigation, and we cannot determine its significant impact on the effectiveness of antibiotic therapy.

Similar to eukaryotes, these hydroxyl radicals are particularly dangerous for bacterial genetic material. Studies indicate that lower concentrations of ROS can be beneficial for bacterial cells, inducing the development of resistance to various environmental factors, including antibiotics [53]. However, bacteria avoid excessive ROS production and can reduce it by modifying their metabolism. An example of such a modification in *P. aeruginosa* is the glyoxylate cycle – abandoning the classical TCA cycle in favor of the glyoxylate cycle reduces NADH production, which, through its oxidation, can directly cause ROS formation [54].

Fluoroquinolones and the antidepressant Fluoxetine can induce ROS formation in *E. coli*. Stimulating ROS formation has therapeutic potential, but it can also be detrimental. Available data indicate that ROS can increase bacterial susceptibility to selected antibiotics, e.g., *E. coli* to Gentamicin; the presence of ROS can also be beneficial for β -lactams, which function better in an aerobic environment [54]. On the other hand, the aforementioned antidepressant led to an increase in the frequency of various types of chromosomal mutations and the expression of genes encoding efflux pumps, which ultimately resulted in the development of resistance to the tested antibiotic [55].

Available literature also points to a connection between ROS formation and rifampicin resistance in *Staphylococcus aureus*: resistant cells exhibited reduced aconitase and succinate dehydrogenase activity, as well as a general decrease in metabolic activity. NAC or glucose alone could restore the cells' susceptibility to the antibiotic. Furthermore, an *in vivo* study showed that mice consuming the antioxidant Tampol before infection responded better to antibiotic therapy. These findings indicate that even in the case of Gram-positive species, combating ROS can play a significant role in therapy [56].

The analysis of ROS's influence on resistance in *P. aeruginosa* also demonstrates that lowering ROS levels can enhance antibiotic susceptibility. Research indicates that Ciprofloxacin used at concentrations lower than MIC can stimulate ROS formation, and thus mutagenesis [57]. Therefore, the use of antioxidants in fluoroquinolone-based antibiotic therapy is justified, as they can slow down the development of antibiotic resistance.

As mentioned earlier, there are data indicating that β -lactams function better in the presence of ROS. This aspect is still under investigation, and one hypothesis is that this mechanism relies on enhanced ROS production, leading to serious intracellular damage, including DNA damage. An interesting aspect is also the change in the synthesis rate of certain metabolites, including compounds that build the cell wall [58].

However, data from the analyzed literature indicate varying behavior of antibiotics in combination with Vitamin C. As noted, changing the vitamin doses combined with fluoroquinolones could shift the behavior from antagonistic to synergistic. As observed in the previous section of the review, ROS elimination should weaken the action of β -lactams, which contradicts some of the results of previously analyzed studies. Trials combining Vitamin C with Tazobactam or Ampicillin do not indicate an antagonistic interaction. We have reason to believe that it might be possible to achieve synergism between these compounds by altering the Vitamin C concentration in the environment.

Furthermore, it cannot be excluded that Vitamin C enhances β -lactams through additional ROS production. This is because, at higher concentrations, ascorbate can have pro-oxidative properties, although there is currently no *in vivo* evidence for such behavior [59].

Preliminarily, we thus hypothesize that the nature of the interaction between Vitamin C and antibiotics (including β -lactam antibiotics) is dependent on the concentrations used, as well as the specific antibiotic itself; more detailed analyses are necessary to verify our claim.

GENETIC REGULATION

Reports on the interaction of Vitamin C with genes and their expression have been published for many years. As Pavlovic notes in his review [60], Vitamin C can regulate gene expression in eukaryotes by:

- Serving as a cofactor for TET enzymes performing DNA demethylation.
- Optimizing the action of JHDM proteins performing lysine demethylation in histones.

Through the regulation of DNA and histone demethylation, Vitamin C regulates the differentiation process of various animal cells, such as those forming bones [61] or blood [62]. These enzymes also require α -ketoglutarate for proper functioning.

In bacteria, alternative enzymes exist with the ability to demethylate DNA bases; an example is AlkB in *E. coli*. In 2002, S.C. Treweek's team analyzed the action of this enzyme and found that it is also dependent on α -ketoglutarate, iron ions, and Vitamin C [63].

However, the above information does not explain the phenomenon of reduced gene expression after treating bacterial cells with Vitamin C; in fact, it contradicts it. Nevertheless, current research proves that elevated concentrations of Vitamin C can inhibit certain transcription factors, such as NF- κ B in eukaryotes, which are essential for the development of cancer cells [64].

Currently, there is a lack of sufficient data to determine the exact mechanism behind the reduction in gene expression in Vitamin C-treated cultures. Chen Xu et al. in their study on hypervirulent strains of *K. pneumoniae*, claim that altered gene expression results from increased ROS formation via the Fenton reaction [50]. However, findings from Rawal's studies provide grounds to believe that an alternative mechanism is the competition of ascorbate with magnesium ions, which are an important cofactor for enzymes, including DNA and RNA polymerases.

IMPACT ON CLINICAL PRACTICE AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

Oxygen therapy is often a fundamental medical procedure used in both emergency care and subsequent hospitalization. Frequent exposure of the respiratory tract to elevated oxygen concentrations can lead to its drying, weakening natural defense mechanisms. In cases of intubation, the risk of infection is particularly increased; ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP) has been described, affecting patients undergoing mechanical ventilation who develop pneumonia after at least 48 hours of intubation. Some estimates indicate that *P. aeruginosa* may account for up to a quarter of such infections [65].

Considering that oxygen therapy is a common element of treatment, we suggest that additional Vitamin C supplementation may have a beneficial effect on treatment outcomes. As noted, exposing macrophages to elevated oxygen concentrations can weaken their effectiveness, an effect that Vitamin C at an easily achievable concentration in the human body abrogated [48]. Additionally, antioxidants can help reduce the intensity of mutagenesis, which can lead to the development of antibiotic resistance.

However, there are several fundamental contraindications for patients using elevated doses of Vitamin C [66]; these include, among others:

- Thalassemia
- Glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase deficiency
- Hemochromatosis
- Diabetes
- Propensity for kidney stone formation and other nephropathies

Most of the *in vivo* studies included in this analysis indicated benefits from incorporating classical Vitamin C into the therapy for infections caused by *P. aeruginosa*. Although intravenous administration of the vitamin is preferred, as it allows for significantly higher plasma concentrations, there are indications that more intensive dietary supplementation (100 vs. 800 mg/kg body weight in guinea pigs) can also reduce mortality or ROS production in the body [49]. The data from Mosallam's study, where the nanoemulsion form worsened the prognosis in *P. aeruginosa*-infected mice but not in *S. aureus* infections, remain unclear [27]. Bedhiafi et al. point out that nanoparticles can have the ability to aggregate [67], while Taghyan et al. demonstrated that silver nanoparticles possess toxic properties, which, however, the presence of Vitamin C partially alleviated [68]. One can speculate that the atypical results observed in Mosallam's study may stem from differences in the cell wall structures of Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria, affecting their interaction with nanoparticles. Additionally, the reduced permeability of the Gram-negative cell wall/membrane to nanoparticles can be taken as an explanation for the results – as such change in permeability has been noticed [69].

Nevertheless, given the current state of available literature, it will be difficult to formulate recommendations for clinical use. The existing data show the therapeutic potential of Vitamin C but are too general to unequivocally determine recommended Vitamin C doses in combination with specific antibiotic dosages. It must be considered that there are reports of antagonistic effects of Vitamin C with antibiotics. For this reason, therapies implementing Vitamin C alongside antibiotics should be considered experimental, but we have reason to believe that they should be considered in specific clinical cases, after excluding the fundamental contraindications listed earlier.

At this moment, we lack sufficient evidence to unequivocally confirm or refute Zięba's and Rawal's claims that Vitamin C constitutes a significant element of therapy. Further high-quality *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies are necessary.

We believe that the further development of research may yield significant practical results in combating not only *P. aeruginosa* but also other pathogens, such as *K. pneumoniae* or *S. aureus*, including antibiotic-resistant strains. Given the complexity of this topic and the variability in bacterial behavior when combining Vitamin C with antibiotics, as well as other compounds, we anticipate that the precise formulation of recommendations for the use of vitamins in such therapies will require complex and extensive research involving multiple research teams. The number of potential combinations for a single strain is significant, arising from the necessity to test different doses of a given antibiotic with various doses of Vitamin C, and the interval between individual doses should be small. Additionally, it should be noted that many other vitamins, besides Vitamin C, can be used in therapy. Marik proposed including a mixture of Vitamin C, thiamine, and hydrocortisone in sepsis therapy [70], but his concept was ultimately not confirmed by clinical trials conducted by other teams [71,72].

It should also be considered that generally, an increase in Vitamin C concentration in an *in vitro* system enhances its bactericidal properties; the phenomenon of stimulating cell growth is concerned with doses below the determined MIC. Currently, we do not have data to determine whether the phenomenon of better bacterial growth at a specific vitamin dose occurs in *in vivo* models. Thus, determining whether and at what doses *in vivo* such phenomena occur can provide a basis for developing preliminary clinical recommendations.

However, the question arises regarding the practical impact of research development on vitamins and antibiotics on healthcare economics, as well as the practicality of widespread therapy selection. Nelson et al. in 2021 estimated the cost of treating 6 drug-resistant species (including drug-resistant *P. aeruginosa*) in the USA at \$4.6 billion annually [73]. Meanwhile, an OECD report indicates that Europe incurs costs of €11.7 billion due to widespread drug resistance [74].

Patients with drug-resistant infections pose not only a challenge for the medical sector, but simultaneously, prolonged therapies entail burdens on the national economy. The ultimate development of recommendations regarding the implementation of vitamins in antibiotic therapy will reduce not only current costs and the healthcare burden but, most importantly, decrease mortality. Further research in this direction will most likely enable the development of an efficient procedure for selecting vitamin and antibiotic concentrations for the specific strain present in a given patient.

The unpopularity of the discussed topic leads to a lack of data. Development of the studies should focus on verifying so far published data, but also should investigate the influence of Vitamin C on other popular antibiotics. For example, 1/5 of prescribed antibiotics in Poland in 2023 were from group J01F [75], which wasn't described in the analyzed research.

FINAL CONCLUSIONS

Previously published studies indicate potential benefits from incorporating Vitamin C into antibiotic therapy, not only for *P. aeruginosa* infections but also for other bacteria. Vitamin C is capable of increasing susceptibility to antibiotics from various groups. Its range of action is broad, encompassing both metabolic changes and effects on gene expression.

However, it is still unclear whether its bacteriostatic action is based on inducing ROS production via the Fenton reaction or if it interacts with other metal ions, such as magnesium. We also still do not understand why the interaction of Vitamin C, for instance, with fluoroquinolones exhibits varying characteristics dependent on the Vitamin C concentrations used. A comprehensive understanding of the molecular mechanism will most likely enable the development of clinical recommendations, as current therapies based on combining antibiotics with high doses of Vitamin C must be categorized as experimental.

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- The authors used AI language models (LLMs) solely for translation of the manuscript from Polish to English. No AI tools were used for data collection, analysis, or original manuscript preparation.
- The authors are ready to share all necessary data upon a request.

CRedit:

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